

SPREAD MODELS APPLIED TO XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA IN OLIVES IN EUROPE

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In the last years, diseases caused by the bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* in several plant species in Europe are generating a considerable ecological, economic and social concerns. In this work, we focus on the potential spread of *X. fastidiosa* in olives in Europe, making an approximation of pathogen dispersal over time. With this objective, different spread scenarios were simulated using the georeferenced layer of olive trees in Europe gathered from the Corine Land Cover inventory. The potentially suitable area for *X. fastidiosa* establishment and spread was defined using an ad hoc Maxent model based on monthly climatic variables obtained from the WorldClim database (Hijmans *et al.*, 2005). Models of radial expansion and logistic growth described by Robinet *et al.* (2012) were projected for a 50-year period. Parameters in both spread models were estimated using the available data of presence and absence of *X. fastidiosa* from the official surveillance program in Apulia, Southern Italy, from 2013 to 2018. For the radial expansion model, the parameter of radial rate of range expansion (km yr⁻¹) was estimated based on the mean Euclidean distance of disease expansion throughout this period. In the case of the logistic growth model, the parameter of relative rate of increase of the invaded area (yr⁻¹) was estimated by nonlinear regression (Ritz and Streibig, 2008) with the Gauss-Newton algorithm. The logistic growth model was implemented using three different spread scenarios; i) grid cells in Europe are invaded randomly, ii) grid cells with olives are invaded first, and iii) grid cells without olives are invaded first. Simulations with the radial expansion model resulted in 53.3% of the cells with olives invaded after 50 years. In the case of the logistic growth model, considering the three spread scenarios, all grid cells with olives in Europe were invaded after 50 years. Nevertheless, models predictions showed to be highly sensitive to parameter values, which were solely based on the observed spread of the disease in Apulia. Furthermore, the assumption that disease dynamics will behave similarly in other European regions may be not equivalent. Therefore, improved methods for parameter estimation are needed, for instance using expert knowledge elicitation.